

Validation questionnaire on the impact of open educational practices focused on social justice

We invite you to participate in a closed-ended questionnaire designed to **validate two open educational practices (OEP) with a focus on social justice**. Your expertise and knowledge in the field of open education and/or equity in learning are essential to enriching these practices prior to their **implementation with initial teacher education students at the University of Lleida during the 2025–2026 academic year**.

Through this questionnaire, we ask you to **evaluate the design and applicability of the two OEP, their alignment with the principles of open education, and their contribution to equity, inclusion, and participation in learning**. Your participation is key to ensuring that these practices effectively address the principles of open education from a social justice perspective.

The two open educational practices to be validated can be accessed at the following links:

- OEP on Digital Footprint: [Digital footprint_OEP I.pdf](#)
- OEP on Bias in Artificial Intelligence: [IA Bias_OEP II.pdf](#)

The first practice, titled *Do you know who you are online? Building an ethical and responsible digital footprint*, aims to help students understand the impact of their digital footprint and take responsibility as digital citizens in creating safe, inclusive, and discrimination-free environments.

The second practice, titled *Artificial intelligence (AI) under the microscope: Uncovering hidden bias and ethical dilemmas*, encourages students to analyze bias in AI, understand its societal impact, and reflect on its ethical implications.

Each document consists of two parts: the first is a systematized summary of the activity developed within the project, including basic information; the second contains the actual educational practice, which should be evaluated and is included in the annex of the document.

This study is part of my doctoral thesis, *"Open Educational Practices in Higher Education for the Development of Critical Digital Competence"* (Dir. Victoria I. Marín), which is itself part of the research project PID2022-1362910A-I00 *"Critical Digital Competence: Toward Agency for Learning through Open Educational Practices"* (CoDiCri: <https://competecs.udl.cat/en/projects/research/codicri/>), led by Dr. Victoria I. Marín. The main objective of the thesis is to study, design, and implement open educational practices in higher education, with a primary focus on social justice, highlighting their interrelation with critical digital competence.

The thesis is funded by the AGAUR-FI Joan Oró Predoctoral Fellowship Program (2024 FI-3 00065) of the Department of Research and Universities of the Government of Catalonia, co-funded by the European Union. The CoDiCri project is funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) of the European Union.

We appreciate your participation in this questionnaire to validate the proposed OEP, as your contribution will provide a broader and more enriching perspective on the design and implementation of educational practices with a focus on social justice.

If you have any questions, please use the contact information below:

CONTACT

María
Faculty of Education,
Department of
COMPETECS
University of Lleida

Abascal

Psychology and Social Work
of Educational
Research

INFORMATION

Guerrero
(FEPTS)
Sciences
Group

maria.abascal@udl.cat

Information on the processing of personal data:

In accordance with current regulations on the protection of personal data, we inform you that:

- The data controller for the personal data provided is the University of Lleida – UdL (Contact details of the representative: General Secretariat, Plaça Víctor Siurana, 1, 25003 Lleida; sg@udl.cat; Contact details of the Data Protection Officer: dpd@udl.cat).
- The data will be used solely for the purposes of this research project and for any other research projects related to the objectives of the current project.
- The statistical data resulting from the project will be stored indefinitely. Other personal data will be retained as long as they are useful for the project or related research projects. They will be deleted according to the terms and conditions established in the UdL's regulations on the conservation and disposal of administrative documents, and in accordance with the documentary evaluation tables approved by the Government of Catalonia (<http://www.udl.cat/ca/serveis/arxiu/>).
- The provision of data is mandatory in order to fulfil the essential purpose of the University of Lleida in offering doctoral studies, training research staff, and promoting scientific research and knowledge transfer to society, in accordance with Organic Law 2/2023, of March 22, on the University System. However, participation in the project is entirely voluntary, and consent, which is necessary for participation, may be withdrawn at any time.
- The UdL will not disclose the data to third parties, except in cases strictly provided for by law. However, since this project is carried out in collaboration with other universities, the data collected and the results obtained in this project may be shared with other entities.
- You may access your data; request its rectification, deletion, or portability; request its limitation; and, in particular, object to its processing (in the latter case, if you provide reasons related to your particular situation), by sending a written request to dpd@udl.cat. You may also file a complaint with the Catalan Data Protection Authority through its electronic headquarters (<https://apdcat.gencat.cat/ca/inici/>) or by other non-electronic means.

Based on the information provided in this document and in the study information sheet, I declare that:

I have read all the information provided; I have understood the explanations clearly presented and have had the opportunity to ask questions to ensure my understanding. I agree to and accept participation in the questionnaire for the validation of open educational practices.

Basic information

1. Gender: F / M / Other (optional question)
2. **Open response:** Professional category
3. **Open response:** Field of specialization/discipline
4. Level of knowledge about OEP and social justice in education (scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = None and 5 = Expert)
5. **Open response:** Years of experience in the field of open educational practices and/or open education
6. **Open response:** Years of experience in the field of social justice in education

OEP to validate: Digital Footprint

Dimension 1: Relationship with the overall design of the practices and their applicability

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

1. The structure of the practice facilitates its implementation in different educational contexts.
2. A clear and concise instructional sequence is proposed that adequately guides the execution of each task.
3. The suggested materials and resources are accessible and appropriate for the development of the practice.
4. The methodology employed promotes student interaction and active learning.
5. The description of the proposal is sufficiently clear for another educator to apply it in any educational context.
6. The practice is aligned with the proposed learning objectives.
7. There are sufficient formative or summative assessment elements to evaluate the level of critical digital competence developed.
8. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding design elements or the applicability of the practice that we should remove, modify, or improve?

Dimension 2: Relation to Open Education

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. The items used in this dimension are based on the definition of OEP proposed by Cronin (2017) and on the conceptual framework of critical digital competence by Marín et al. (2024, under review), which can be found in CoDiCri (2025).

Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

CoDiCri (2024). *Un marco conceptual de la competencia digital crítica*. COMPETECS.

https://competecs.udl.cat/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/CDC_marcoconceptual_CODICRI_ES.pdf

Cronin, C. (2017). Openness and Praxis: Exploring the Use of Open Educational Practices in Higher Education. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18(5).

<https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v18i5.3096>

Marín, V. I., Orellana-Hernández, M. L., Tur, G., Villagrà, S., Peguera-Carré, M. C., & Castañeda, L. (en revisión). A Conceptual Framework for Critical Digital Competence: Creation and Validation.

1. The designed practice has a Creative Commons license that allows the reuse and/or adaptation of content in different educational contexts.
2. The designed practice creates, uses, and/or reuses Open Educational Resources (OER), thereby promoting open access to these resources without restrictions.
3. The methodological strategies employed facilitate co-creation of knowledge.
4. The methodological strategies employed promote student empowerment.
5. The methodological strategies employed support open teaching.
6. Extended learning beyond the classroom is encouraged.
7. Peer learning is promoted.
8. The use of participatory technologies and social networks that enable collaboration, interaction, and/or participation is proposed.
9. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding aspects of the design or applicability of the practice in relation to open education that should be removed, modified, or improved?

Dimension 3: Relation to Social Justice

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

1. The designed practice addresses relevant social issues.
2. The designed practice promotes critical reflection by the student.
3. The practice fosters responsible digital citizenship based on equity and respect for social rights.
4. The practice encourages analysis and discussion of social, cultural, and economic inequalities present in the digital environment.

5. The practice promotes equity in access to information and digital tools used within the proposed activities.
6. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding aspects of the design or applicability of the practice related to social justice that should be removed, modified, or improved?
7. **Open response:** What improvements or adjustments would you suggest to further strengthen the social justice focus?

OEP to validate: Biases in Artificial Intelligence

Dimension 1: Relationship with the overall design of the practices and their applicability

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

1. The structure of the practice facilitates its implementation in different educational contexts.
2. A clear and concise instructional sequence is proposed that adequately guides the execution of each task.
3. The suggested materials and resources are accessible and appropriate for the development of the practice.
4. The methodology employed promotes student interaction and active learning.
5. The description of the proposal is sufficiently clear for another educator to apply it in any educational context.
6. The practice is aligned with the proposed learning objectives.
7. There are sufficient formative or summative assessment elements to evaluate the level of critical digital competence developed.
8. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding design elements or the applicability of the practice that we should remove, modify, or improve?

Dimension 2: Relation to Open Education

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. The items used in this dimension are based on the definition of OEP proposed by Cronin (2017) and on the conceptual framework of critical digital competence by Marín et al. (2024, under review), which can be found in CoDiCri (2025).

Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

CoDiCri (2024). *Un marco conceptual de la competencia digital crítica*. COMPETECS.

https://competecs.udl.cat/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/CDC_marcoconceptual_CODICRI_ES.pdf

Cronin, C. (2017). Openness and Praxis: Exploring the Use of Open Educational Practices in Higher Education. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18(5).

<https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v18i5.3096>

1. The designed practice has a Creative Commons license that allows the reuse and/or adaptation of content in different educational contexts.
2. The designed practice creates, uses, and/or reuses Open Educational Resources (OER), thereby promoting open access to these resources without restrictions.
3. The methodological strategies employed facilitate co-creation of knowledge.
4. The methodological strategies employed promote student empowerment.
5. The methodological strategies employed support open teaching.
6. Extended learning beyond the classroom is encouraged.
7. Peer learning is promoted.
8. The use of participatory technologies and social networks that enable collaboration, interaction, and/or participation is proposed.
9. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding aspects of the design or applicability of the practice in relation to open education that should be removed, modified, or improved?

Dimension 3: Relation to Social Justice

Please answer each question considering the OEP you are currently evaluating. Respond using the following scale: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree.

1. The designed practice addresses relevant social issues. The designed practice promotes critical reflection by the student.
2. The practice fosters responsible digital citizenship based on equity and respect for social rights.
3. The practice encourages analysis and discussion of social, cultural, and economic inequalities present in the digital environment.
4. The practice promotes equity in access to information and digital tools used within the proposed activities.
5. **Open response:** Do you have any suggestions regarding aspects of the design or applicability of the practice related to social justice that should be removed, modified, or improved?
6. **Open response:** What improvements or adjustments would you suggest to further strengthen the social justice focus?

Open-ended questions

1. What other aspects or elements would you add to improve the applicability of these practices?
2. Is there anything else you would like to add?